

Modelling strategy of IR lamps with integrated reflector used in the manufacturing process of thermoplastic composite tapes

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Context: Slurry impregnation of thermoplastic unidirectional tape

Impregnation line (IRT SE)

Modelling of Infrared oven
IR lamps with integrated reflector

Radiation distribution of lamps with integrated reflector

Lamp with integrated reflector

Experimental setup

Halogen lamp

Infrared Camera
FLIR SC325 [7.5-13] μm

Results

Non homogeneous spatial distribution

How to model lamp with integrated reflector?

Adaptation of clear lamp modelling strategy

- Quartz tube + Spiralled filament → Equivalent cylinder $\phi=11mm$
- Temperature → Filament temperature
- Emissivity $\epsilon = \epsilon_f(T) R_{lf} / R_{lt}$
- Weighted Radiosity $= k_{li} \epsilon(T) \sigma T^4$

Parameter Optimisation using inverse analysis

Experimental data
Voltage: 400V (100%)
Filament temperature
2450K

- Optimisation variables $k_{l1}, k_{l2}, k_{l3}, k_{l4}, k_{l5}, k_{l6}, h$
- Objective function $\min_{\tau} \sum_i (T_{inum} - T_{lexp} / T_{lexp})^2$
- Constraints $k_{li} \leq k_{li+1}$
 $0.8 \leq \sum_{i=1}^6 k_{li} \leq 1.2$

Optimised temperature field
Surface error : 7,02%

	Initial Value	Optimised Value
k1	0.3	0.4997
k2	0.2	0.1669
k3	0.17	0.1667
k4	0.16	0.0853
k5	0.13	0.0852
k6	0.05	0.0851
Σk_i	1.01	1.0893
h (W/m ² .K)	2	1.31
CPU Laptop		15h

Preliminary model of industrial oven

Experimental setup

Heating of ABS sheet instrumented with type K thermocouples

Experimental vs Model

Good results for central point during heating.

- Poor spatial distribution
- Natural convection is considered in place of forced convection.
- Glass plates are neglected. Low lamp temperatures could lead to absorption by these plates.

Perspectives

Oven model

- Glass plates should be included in future work
- Convection should be improved by experimental measurements

Material characterisation

- Unidirectional carbon fiber -PAEK prepreg characterisation
- On line experiments (Impregnation line)